

IMPROVING COHERENCE IN TECHNICAL WRITING

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Abstract: Even when spelling and punctuation issues are properly handled, many unskilled student writers' technical documents still fail to effectively communicate. This happens even though the student may be knowledgeable in the subject since they are not clear in their minds about the elements that need to be presented. Additionally, efficient communication techniques are not well defined, making it challenging for novice writers to comprehend them. This article discusses coherence, which is one of the more challenging elements for beginning writers yet has the potential to significantly improve communication. This article seeks to offer an organized method for instructors to follow when helping students develop their technical writing abilities.

Keywords: effective communication, technical writing, coherence

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that graduate and undergraduate engineering students need to become proficient in efficient technical communication, and a number of useful recommendations have been made to do so. Although effective speaking, writing, reading, and listening skills are all important components of excellent communication (accessed on February 3, 2003), we often focus on helping students improve their speaking (presentation) and writing abilities. It is typically more harder to master writing abilities between the two. This is most likely a result of the increased discipline and clarity that good writing demands. Additionally, there is a prevalent belief that writing skills are learned experientially, much like learning to ride a bike, play an instrument, or swim.

Coherence

Assuming that the language (grammar, spelling, and pronunciation) aspects are properly addressed, good communication results from good knowledge in the subject matter, a clear awareness of the aspects that need to be communicated (and the aspects that need to be left out), clear thinking, and good organization. Knowing how the reader or listener will interpret the information is necessary for the best organization. In other words, it helps to be able to "tell a story" or clearly deliver the pertinent information. In fact, when students present their study, many counselors may ask, "What is your story?" Because the communicator is absent when the recipient receives a written message, the aforementioned requirements become much more crucial.

Tools for Coherence

The development of a systematic, logical presentation sequence, as outlined in a later section, might be encouraged among students. We will now discuss some strategies that can be used to enhance the coherence and, consequently, the conveyance of the material after it has been logically sequenced (see Kies, papyr.com/hypertextbooks/engl126/book126.htm, accessed on 3rd February 2003). Let's look at a well-written piece by Bird [11], which has been somewhat modified here, to better understand the use of tools: In educational circles today, teaching and research are topics that are frequently discussed. However, book writing, which should be listed as the third primary activity of a university teacher because it directly relates to the creation, assessment, organization, and transmission of new knowledge, receives very little attention. The "rites, benefits, and obligations" of book authorship, I reasoned, could be beneficial to emphasize in this talk. As a co-author of multiple books, I've had the pleasure and good fortune to do so, so perhaps I can encourage new authors in the right way and perhaps offer some advice on the craft. Maybe I can prevent some of the errors I've made from happening to others. I will occasionally use specific examples from my own life to avoid talking about authorship issues in an abstract way.

Repeating ideas helps to make sentences more coherent. To create coherence, Bird uses the word "book(s)" several times in the example above. If repetition gets monotonous, a synonym can be employed; for instance, in the first phrase of the last paragraph presented, Bird uses the word "volumes" to prevent a monotonous repeat of the word "books." Similar to this, Antonymy can strengthen coherence by doing the opposite; for instance, observe how "impractical concepts" and "reliable tools" are used in the same sentence in the last paragraph of Bird's passage (Bp). The pronoun is frequently used to increase the coherence between phrases; for instance, in the first paragraph of Bp, the pronoun "it" is used to refer to "book-writing." Additionally, coherence is enhanced by parallelism, which is the usage of the same phrase structure in succeeding sentences.

Enumeration, which refers to the use of particular markers of sequence to make the connection between the thoughts offered, is a tool that engineers frequently utilize. In the second paragraph of Bp, Bird utilizes enumeration to connect the various groups of books, which is a nice example of enumeration in use.

Transition is a tool that children may pick up quickly. Conjunctions or conjunctive adverbs, often known as transition words, are used to connect sentences with certain logical ties. The following subcategories can be made based on their meaning: Identity. signifies similarity: to put it another way

The Preliminaries

1. Before starting to write, the learner must acquire the necessary background knowledge or information. This is a requirement that must be met.
2. If a report, thesis, or manuscript for a journal has to be produced, a significant number of

Before the learner starts writing, they must understand the conversation components (let's say 50%). Therefore, it is important to urge students to carefully study scientific content and to clearly note down the key discussion points before writing. Many first manuscript manuscripts include weak data/simulation discussion.

3. The pupil must be at ease. You can advise him or her to sip on some water and take a few deep breathes, being careful to exhale more slowly than they inhaled.

The student should then get some blank pages, a pencil and eraser, or a word processor, and find a quiet area to sit.

the inquiries

The learner should now reflect on the italicized questions below and apply the suggested solutions. I'll give an example of my own thought process from a few years back when I was writing a paper to serve as an illustration.

What is the major concept I need to convey?

For instance, we were really excited when we learned that induced free radicals could increase the productivity of cells in bioreactors. Because of this, the major message we needed to convey was that "generated free radicals can be exploited as a novel approach to boost bioreactor productivity." For novice writers, identifying the essential message that must be conveyed may take some consideration. But that is where you should begin.

2. How should I present the primary idea?

It's not too complicated, he Preliminaries

1. Before starting to write, the learner must acquire the necessary background knowledge. This is a requirement that must be met.

2. A significant portion of the discussion components (let's say, 50%) must be understood by the student before the writing process begins if a manuscript for journal publication, a thesis, or a report is to be written. Therefore, it is important to urge students to carefully study scientific content and to clearly note down the key discussion points before writing. Many first manuscript manuscripts include weak data/simulation discussion. 3. The pupil must be at ease. You can advise him or her to sip on some water and take a few deep breathes, being careful to exhale more slowly than they inhaled. The student should then get some blank pages, a pencil and eraser, or a word processor, and find a quiet area to sit.

Effectiveness of the Structured Approach

The students at IIT Bombay pursuing the communication skills course were given the same planned approach. Additionally, they were given writing exercises (and presentation). Their writing (as well as presentation) skills) considerably improved. Students expressed gratitude for the course.

They received an offer. Even students who were fluent in the language at first expressed skepticism about the course's relevance to them. These pupils discovered that being able to write properly does not guarantee good communication. These students also stated that the course had a big impact on their lives.

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